

Institute *of* **Physics**

**Environmental
Physics Group**

Newsletter

February 2001

Editor's Report

This is the first of three Newsletters for 2001, and the main item of information is the meeting on The Physical Environment and Health at Physics Congress in Brighton on Wednesday 21 March. We have an attractive programme and it is hoped that many members will participate. Please note that Dr. Oliver's talk is now entitled The Relations between Soil and Human Health.

I also draw your attention to the Annual General Meeting on Wednesday 16 May followed by a talk from Dennis Anderson on The Prospects for Renewable Energy, a topic of increasing importance for the future welfare of our planet.

There will also be a half-day meeting in London on Wednesday 31 October jointly with the Environmental Chemistry Group of the Royal Society of Chemistry to discuss the topic Environment and Sustainable Agriculture. Further details will be in the June Newsletter.

Derek Rose

Environmental Physics Group Bulletin Board

The Environmental Physics Group is pleased to launch an electronic Bulletin Board where Members of the Environmental Physics Group can post any questions or queries that they would like answers to. It could also be used to highlight any events that they think other EPG members would be interested in.

However, in order to use the Board, Members of the Group need first to be registered with PhysicsWeb. To register with PhysicsWeb please go to <http://physicsweb.org/register>

Once you have received your PhysicsWeb Username and Password, you will be able to access the Bulletin Board via the link on the Environmental Physics Group Home Page at <http://www.iop.org/IOP/Groups/EP/>

We hope that this service will provide an exciting and valuable addition to our activities.

Alexandra Wilson

The Physical Environment and Health

Announcement

Meeting at Physics Congress, Brighton, Wednesday 21st March 2001

As the activities of human populations change through scientific, technological and social developments, so we have to acknowledge that changes in the environmental systems we inhabit will be a likely consequence. Climate change, the ozone hole and electromagnetic radiation from power lines and mobile telephones are well-publicised examples of environmental conditions that have been linked to effects on human health and led to high levels of public concern.

The natural environment has always posed a health risk and this meeting will seek to put into context the impact of man-made and naturally occurring environmental conditions on health. Expert speakers will explore links, established and potential, between the physical environment in which we live and human health and examine the evidence for mechanisms, in the environment and in the body, underlying effects on health. The assessment of risks associated with changing environmental conditions and how the link to policy decisions is made will also be considered.

Speakers

B L Diffey (Newcastle General Hospital, "Ozone Depletion and Skin Cancer: Alarming or Alarmist?")

P S Excell (University of Bradford, "Mobile Communications Technologies and Dosimetric Procedures for Human Exposure Assessment")

J W Hand (Imperial College School of Medicine, "Mobile Telephones and Health")

J K Haywood (South Cleveland Hospital, "What Precautionary Principle?")

A J McMichael (London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, "Health Effects of Global Environmental Change")

M A Oliver (Reading University, "Geostatistics as an aid to explore relations between the environment and human health")

A W Preece (Bristol University, "Power Frequency Electromagnetic Fields and Humans - are there Health Effects?")

J Swanson (National Grid Company, "Power-Frequency Electric and Magnetic Fields - Moving From Science to Policy")

A Congress registration fee will apply. EPG Travel Bursaries will be available to assist EPG members in attending the meeting. For further information please contact:

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Meeting organised by the Environmental Physics and Medical Physics Groups of the Institute of Physics.

NOTICE

10th Annual General Meeting of the Environmental Physics Group

The 10th Annual General Meeting of the Environmental Physics Group will be held on **Wednesday 16th May 2001** at 5:30pm. The meeting will be held in the Rutherford Conference Centre at the Institute of Physics' headquarters at 76 Portland Place, London.

There is one vacancy for an Ordinary Committee Member this year. Nominations must be sent to the Honorary Secretary not later than seven days before the AGM. Nominations should be proposed by not less than two Members of the Group and should be accompanied by the written consent of the nominee.

Following the AGM, a talk on renewable energy will be given by Professor Dennis Anderson, head of the Imperial College Centre for Energy Policy and Technology, commencing at 6:30pm. The meeting will close with discussion and refreshments.

A limited number of EPG travel bursaries will be available to assist members of the EPG attending this meeting.

I look forward to seeing you at the AGM.

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The Charles Chree Award

The Institute of Physics has awarded this year's Charles Chree Medal and Prize to Joseph Farman, Brian Gardiner and Jonathon Shanklin of the British Antarctic Survey for their part in the discovery of the "ozone hole" over the Antarctic and for linking this to the growth of CFCs in the atmosphere. The Award is made annually for distinguished research in environmental physics, terrestrial magnetism, atmospheric electricity and related subjects, such as other aspects of geophysics comprising the earth, oceans, atmosphere and solar-terrestrial problems.

Stratospheric ozone plays an exceptional role in protecting the earth from the sun's harmful ultraviolet radiation by its ability to absorb the major part of this dangerous radiation. Without the protective ozone layer in the atmosphere, animal and plant life could not exist, at least upon land. By the early 1980s atmospheric physicists and chemists were confident that a good understanding of the formation and decomposition of ozone through chemical processes in the atmosphere was developing, with observations and models agreeing. However, the paper by Farman, Gardiner and Shanklin in *Nature* in 1985 proved everyone wrong.

Ozone depletion over the Antarctic was first noticed by Farman and his co-workers in 1982. They didn't make any sensational announcements in the scientific press. Instead, like true experimentalists, they checked the instrument calibration and shipped a new spectrophotometer to the Antarctic to double-check their observations. By October 1994 the British Antarctic Survey team were convinced that their observations were correct, despite the fact that satellites had failed to report any decrease.

Not only did they report the decline of ozone, they also speculated on the reason for it. In particular they pointed out that "the present day atmosphere differs most prominently from that of previous decades in the higher concentrations of halocarbons". They suggested that the very low temperatures over Antarctica from midwinter to early spring might make the stratosphere there "uniquely sensitive to the growth of inorganic chloride", an assessment that now has been proved to be correct after several years of intensive research.

It was their discovery of the "ozone hole" that was the driving force behind the first global treaty to combat pollution - the Montreal protocol. By careful observation, the three researchers have contributed to our salvation from a global environmental problem that could have catastrophic consequences. The three scientists worked as a team. Farman's contribution was on the dynamics and chemistry of the atmosphere, Gardiner's was on the spectrometric techniques, and Shanklin was involved with the observations and the data reduction. The three working together was a requisite for the successful discovery, and it is fitting that recognition be given for this by making the Charles Chree Award jointly to the three researchers.

"Foresight" and Climatic Change

Foresight

The Foresight programme was launched in 1994 and renewed by the present government. The programme is to develop visions of the future and is "focussed on wealth creation and quality of life". It is difficult in a short note to describe its function properly: interested readers should apply for a copy of "Blueprint" (Foresight) from the Office of Science and Technology. ⁽¹⁾

Foresight is divided into sectoral panels: of particular interest to the Environmental Physics Group are the panels on

Energy and Natural Environment

Built Environment and Transport

Several consultation documents have been received by the I.O.P. for comment, to which your committee has contributed. These are

Foresight - Energy and Natural Environment - A Way to Go

Foresight - Energy and Natural Environment - Making Sustainability Count

Copies of these documents ⁽¹⁾ and of the I.O.P. responses ⁽²⁾ are available.

Climate Change

The deliberations of the Foresight panels will be affected by climate change. According to the consensus of scientific opinion: (a) global warming has commenced and will continue, (b) it is caused largely by the "greenhouse effect" due to human activity and not by some natural mechanism, and (c) the modifications to climate for the next 40 or 50 years have already been determined in that any remedies introduced now would only benefit the second half of the 21st century. This is the most likely scenario but, of course, cannot be a certain one. Furthermore any reduction of greenhouse gases by the U.K. would occur with probably minimal reductions elsewhere in the world.

In a separate initiative the I.O.P. held a seminar on Climate Change in October 2000. A summary report is available. ⁽²⁾

Another consultation document (driven by the prospect of climate change) received by the I.O.P. from the Department of Trade and Industry concerns the "Renewable Obligation", which would place legal obligations upon all licensed electricity suppliers to provide a specified proportion from sources of renewable energy. Copies of the document ⁽³⁾ and of the I.O.P. submission are available. ⁽²⁾

References

- (1) Office of Science and Technology, 1 Victoria St., London SW1H 0ET, Tel. 020 7215 6722
- (2) Public Affairs, The Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London W1B 1NT, Tel. 020 7470 4800
- (3) Sustainable Energy Policy Unit, Department of Trade and Industry, 1 Victoria Street, London SW1H 0ET, Tel. 020 7215 6722

Douglas Peirson

Institute of Physics Benevolent Fund

The Institute of Physics Benevolent Fund was established in 1924 by the first honorary treasurer, Major CES Philips. Over the years the fund has grown through the generosity of members of the Institute and members are still encouraged to support the fund by donations and bequests.

The fund exists to provide support for physicists and their close dependents during times of hardship. This may include bereavement, ill health, disability, accident or old age. The fund can provide or contribute towards the cost of special needs, equipment or adaptations to property to improve the quality of life. It can also offer short-term financial assistance towards respite care to enable carers to benefit from a well-earned break.

The trustees welcome requests for assistance and all are treated in the strictest confidence. Letters marked Private and Confidential should be addressed to Mrs Susan Dowling, Secretary of the Benevolent Fund, 76 Portland Place, London W1B 1NT. The Committee meets periodically during the year to consider applications for support but procedures exist to deal quickly with urgent cases.

Members considering a bequest to the fund should contact the Secretary for further information.

Committee of the EPG

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